

Proposed Marketing Initiative to Increase Brand Awareness and Purchase Conversion Case Study Brand: Ajoy Biscuit Stick

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ABSTRACT: One of the brand portfolios that is expected to grow to support Claygo's commercial expansion in Indonesia especially in the biscuit category is Ajoy. According to the 2020–2021 results, Ajoy is dealing with significant business issues, such as unmet sales targets that are negatively related to category growth. Ajoy's penetration rate is likewise still very low, at less than 1%, with a trialist base of just 0.6 to 0.8 percent. This study uses a quantitative approach with the type of descriptive research. The approach to obtain the data is done with the survey by utilizing online questionnaires. Ajoy brand awareness is relatively poor, primarily due to the advertisement's low share of voice. Low purchase conversion results from low awareness, which is also a result of a number of barriers, including product knowledge, price, and physical and mental availability. Due to Ajoy's higher pricing but unable to establish a solid judgment regarding the price point, the premium positioning it seeks to establish is not well received by the target market. This study will help Ajoy to identify its low brand awareness trigger and low purchase conversion (from aware to ever purchase metric) trigger, as well as develop the brand message corresponding to Ajoy's premium positioning and define the integrated marketing communication initiatives to deliver the brand message to Ajoy's prime prospect.

KEYWORDS: Brand awareness, Brand message, Integrated marketing communication, Purchase conversion.

INTRODUCTION

The food sector is the biggest contributor with 35% share of the total FMCG business in Indonesia. The food sector consists of the snack and confectionery (snacking) segment which makes up 13% of total Food FMCG and managed to post positive performance with 12% growth in the past 12 months versus last year (NielsenIQ, December 2021).

Snacking is necessary for Indonesians to support their mental and emotional well-being, not merely to avoid hunger. Snacking time is used by eighty six percent of Indonesian respondents to build and sustain togetherness with others. This behavior is part of the Indonesian culture of utilizing delicacies or snacks as "ice-breakers" and to keep people together. Indonesians have used snacks as gifts to eat together and interact with one another for generations as a very sociable society.

The biggest category of the snacking segment is the biscuit category. Biscuit category contributes to almost half of the snacking market with 41.5% of value share and 56% of volume share. By the end of 2021, the biscuit category is showing fast growth compared to last year with 11% growth and manages to be on the top four of fastest growing FMCG category worth IDR 26 billion. The top 10 players in this category are dominated by local manufacturers such Mayora with the biggest market share, followed by Kaldu Sari Nabati which has the value of half of Mayora. The other local players are Garuda Food, Ultra Prima Abadi, Khong Guan, Nissin, and Asia Sakti Wahid which have 5.8% of value shares on average. While the global manufacturers in this top 10 rank are dominated by Mondelez International from the USA, Arnotts from Australia, and Claygo from Japan with 4% of value shares on average.

Claygo Indonesia currently only plays in the stick biscuit category with its three international brands. One of the brand portfolios that is expected to grow to support Claygo's commercial expansion in Indonesia especially in the biscuit category is Ajoy. According to the 2020–2021 results, Ajoy is dealing with significant business issues, such as unmet sales targets that are negatively related to category growth. Ajoy's penetration rate is likewise still very low, at less than 1%, with a trialist base of just 0.6 to 0.8 percent. Ajoy is experiencing a very tense struggle to penetrate the brand in the market. According to brand health tracking data and management explanation, the main problems that drive the brand having low penetration are:

Thus, this study will help Ajoy to identify its low brand awareness trigger and low purchase conversion (from aware to ever purchase metric) trigger, as well as develop the brand message corresponding to Ajoy's premium positioning and define the integrated marketing communication initiatives to deliver the brand message to Ajoy's prime prospect.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness plays an important role in consumer decision-making, market performance, marketing mix, and brand equity. It is the first funnel of a brand's touch point to consumers. Keller (2008) has pointed out that brand awareness refers to whether consumers can recall or recognize a brand, or simply whether consumers know about a brand. Based on study from Nielsen and IPSOS, the brand awareness is divided into unaided and aided brand awareness. Unaided awareness is the percentage of respondents aware of product, brand, or advertising top-of-mind without being assisted. In this research survey, respondents were asked: "What brands of sweet biscuit come to your mind?". The aided brand awareness is a measure of the number of people who express knowledge or awareness of a brand or product when prompted.

Customer Moment of Truth Journey

A 'Moment of Truth' can be considered an experience with the product that will influence buying behavior. The concept of the Moment of Truth was introduced in the 1980s by Jan Carlzon. Some 20 years later, in 2005, A.G. Lafley, Chairman, President and CEO of Procter & Gamble, came up with his version of Moments of Truth. Then in 2011 Google came up with another Moment of Truth, which it referred to as the Zero Moment of Truth (ZMOT) which completed the journey.

The foundation of the Moment of Truth is rooted in the 4-step mental model of marketing. These steps can be defined as:

- Stimulus which is the catalyst induced by a brand's marketing activity to make consumers considering the product,
- Zero Moment of truth is when the consumer finally recognizes a brand or product then they researches further about the product prior to purchase.
- First Moment of Truth which is the on hands experience with the product at the point of purchase,
- Second Moment of Truth which is the experience buying and using the product.

By the growth of the internet of things and social media which enable consumers to speak about the brand easily, the step is now completed with the ultimate moment of truth, which is the moment when consumers share about their experience to others or often mention it as advocacy. In every moment of truth stage, marketers can take the opportunity to present and connect the brand with target consumers. Thus, the brand can give ultimate experience for the consumers and keep the cycle stable.

Customer Path to Purchase

In the era of digital connectivity, the framework to describe the customer journey has shifted from AIDA (attention, interest, desire and action) to 5A which comprises aware, appeal, ask, act and advocate (Kotler, Kertajaya & Setiawan, 2016). In the awareness phase, customers are passively exposed to a long list of products from past experience that could be gained from several information sources such as inner circle recommendation, social media or the customer's past experience in using the brand. The key word in this phase is "I know". The next phase is appeal, this is where customers create short term memory of amplifying the long-term memory then become attracted to short-lists of brands. The key word in the appeal phase is "I like" After the customers get appealed, they will search for more detailed information related to the products that they are attracted to. The key word in this phase is "I'm convinced". The next phase after being convinced, the customers are taking action to buy the products which are marked by the keyword "I'm buying". The last phase is when customers create new positive memories on their last buy, they will advocate the products to others. This phrase is marked by the keyword "I recommend".

Brand Message and Attribute

Generally, branding seeks to change audience perceptions of a brand in order to convince them to select it over rivals. The brand message permeates the mind and impacts perceptions, while the logo and graphics may catch the eye. Every message a brand conveys to the audience across all touch points is referred to as brand messaging. Therefore it must nourish the perception with everything marketers want the audience to know about the brand in order to give it the best chance of continuing to exist in their minds with the aimed perception. Every brand has a unique value proposition which is rooted from any attributes compiling to the brand. Brand attributes are a bundle of features that highlight the physical and personality aspects of the brand. Attributes are

developed through images, actions, or presumptions. Brand attributes help in shaping unique value propositions and creating brand identity.

Integrated Marketing Communication

Integrated marketing communications (IMC) is Carefully integrating and coordinating the company’s many communications channels to deliver a clear, consistent, and compelling message about the organization and its products (Kotler, Amstrong, Opemnick, 2018).

Conceptual Framework

This study is initiated from the background of the study which covers the business landscape of FMCG sector particularly snack & biscuit category in Indonesia, the company background of Claygo Indonesia and one of Claygo’s brand portfolios, Ajoy, a center – filled biscuit brand which will be the main study of this research.

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework, Analysed by Researcher

The collected data, fact, and information has helped to identify current business challenges faced by the company which has unachieved sales targets due to low brand penetration. Furthermore, two main problems which may cause the hurdle are identified. Firstly, the brand has a low conversion rate and secondly the brand does not have strong brand positioning. From those two main problem statements, research objectives are defined as 1) identify its low brand awareness trigger 2) identify low purchase conversion (from aware to ever purchase metric) trigger 3) develop the brand message corresponding to Ajoy’s premium positioning 4) define the integrated marketing communication initiatives to deliver the brand message to Ajoy’s prime prospect.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative approach with the type of descriptive research which is used to describe the characteristics of a particular object. The approach to obtain the data is done with the survey by utilizing online questionnaires. In this research, the information gathered from the survey will be focused on the certain factors which affect brand awareness and purchase behavior as well as certain attributes on the brand building aspects, and all measurement indicators have been defined. It will uncover detailed information which is needed to solve the case case study.

Figure 2. Research Methodology, Analysed by Researcher

The primary data in this research is obtained through quantitative sampling via online questionnaires. The questionnaire structure is divided into 5 parts: screening questions which aims to understand respondent profile, brand health checking which aims to know the awareness level of the listed brands, brand image profiling based on general perception on sweet biscuit category drivers/attributes, sweet biscuit consumption occasion, perceived premium imageries, and current media consumption.

With the use of semantic differential scale, the chosen attributes and their degree of importance as per respondent's feedback will act as a base for collecting insights from the primary data. The attributes will later determine what are the points-of-difference that potentially can be owned and emphasized by Ajoy.

Referring from Mridusmita Das (2020), the analysis technique involved the following stages:

Stage 1: through online questionnaires, the respondents were asked to score the identified attributes with *the degree of importance* of the specific attribute on a scale of 1 to 7 in their sweet biscuit purchasing behaviour, in general.

Stage 2 : through online questionnaires, the respondents then were asked to score the selected six brands namely Ajoy, Rocky, Oreo, Astor, BengBeng, Chocolatos on a scale of 1 to 5 per attribute.

Stage 3: identify the consumers' perception on each attribute towards the selected brands

After following the three stages of analysis, researcher will examine each attribute that respondents have scored for Ajoy to identify what are potential attributes that can be improved and owned.

The list of competing brands are listed as below:

- Rocky as it comes within the same stick biscuit category and has the same product format as well as pack format which sometimes people misunderstand Ajoy as Rocky the reverse,
- Oreo as it always becomes a top of mind brand in the biscuit category and the product portfolio could cater multiple segments which contribute to its high penetration and market share,
- Astor has a similar format of center filled snack with flavored chocolate. astor has existed in the Indonesia market for a long time and became the pioneer of center filled format. Hence when Ajoy came in, it was recognized as astor due to the similar product format,
- Chocolatos as it has same concern with astor which Ajoy was misattributed as Chocolatos due to same product format and product visual on its previous campaign,
- Bengbeng as it offers similar chocolate delicacy/pleasure and also it comes top of mind after Rocky and Oreo.

FINDINGS AND ARGUMENT

BRAND AWARENESS

How is Ajoy’s brand awareness situation currently?

In terms of top of mind awareness in the sweet biscuit category, Ajoy was mentioned by only a few people while the most mentioned brands were Oreo and Rocky. In terms of total awareness, Ajoy is still facing the lowest score among the competitors. In Aided brand awareness Oreo, Rocky, and Astor are leading the chart. However, Ajoy is gaining the lowest aided brand awareness score among those five competitor brands. Thus, in total awareness, Ajoy is still facing the lowest score among the competitors. The result is corresponding to the brand health tracking which was conducted by IPSOS in 2021 which also shows that Ajoy brand awareness is considered low with only 0% of unaided awareness and 48% of total awareness which is mostly driven by aided awareness. It is below category norms which other brands mostly have above 60% total awareness, it drags the brand out of the consumer radar.

Figure 3. Aided Brand Awareness, Analysed by Researcher

Does Ajoy already tap into the right media touch points to reach its prime prospect?

During 2021, Ajoy was running TV terrestrial advertisements for 3 months only, precisely in October, November and December. The average Share of Voice (SOV) that Ajoy had was around 2.5% which was quite low in the category. While on digital platforms, Ajoy managed to present on Youtube during non-TV periods. On Facebook and Instagram platform, Ajoy managed to present on an always-on basis which means the platform was run during January through December. Ajoy also utilized several key opinion leaders (KOL) in Instagram platform which reflect its target audience. Unfortunately Ajoy barely leverages any media touch points or activities to encourage advocacy. Basically, there is no issue on Ajoy’s media touch point as the brand has chosen the right target to reach the prime audiences. Ajoy’s prime prospect audience is set for females, 25-40 years old. The findings show that ajoy ads has been able to reach the prime prospect over other audience groups. Nevertheless, though Ajoy has tapped to the right media touch point, it is needed to check further on the competitiveness level and seek possible findings that caused the low brand awareness.

Figure 4. Brand Share of Voice 2021, Claygo Data

Brand	Share of Voice (%)
Astor	1%
BengBeng	7%
Rocky	6%
Oreo	5%
Chocolatos	4%
Ajoy	3%

How is Ajoy’s advertisement competitiveness compared with other competing brands in terms of brand advertisement recognition?

demographic	TV	YT	IG	FB	POSM	Tiktok	Digital Ads Banner	Twitter	KOL
Male	51	54	20	17	21	14	15	3	3
Female	54	34	24	15	10	9	7	6	5
18 – 24	45	43	14	5	19	5	14	2	7
25 – 29	64	45	30	19	15	21	6	4	2
30 – 34	58	50	23	23	12	15	12	8	8
35 – 39	61	36	27	15	12	6	9	3	3
40 – 44	35	50	12	12	21	9	12	-	-
45 – 49	50	39	28	33	11	11	17	17	6

Figure 5. Ads Recognition Across Group 2021, Claygo Data

Based on researcher’s primary data through an online questionnaire, the result shows that 75% of the respondents recognized Ajoy advertisements across different media. But other competing brands receive higher recognition which leads to very crowded circumstances in consumer’s mind which also impact the share of voice. The share of voice of Ajoy during 2021 was relatively low. The low SOV of Ajoy surely contributes to the low competitiveness and leads to low awareness as well. In terms of social listening, Ajoy has the lowest number of mentions and total impressions with only 351 mentions and 5.68 million total impressions during the

year-to-date 2022, While other competing brands manage to achieve 4.5 thousand mentions in average and 44 million impressions in average.

PURCHASE CONVERSION

How is current Ajoy’s conversion rate in its customer path to purchase funnel situation?

The upper funnel which includes awareness and conversion from aware to ever purchased stage and it has become the most important stage to reach initial consumer baseline. Total awareness of Ajoy is only reaching 48 points while other brands could reach above 80% and for conversion from awareness to ever purchase which become the main highlight, Ajoy is reaching only 28% which is still half of category average. It is shown that Ajoy is less preferred by the customer in this category. Perhaps, Ajoy could be considered out of radar or having weak mental availability for most of the sweet biscuit consumers due to the low brand familiarity and knowledge of the unique selling proposition which may cause consumers to have low reason to purchase Ajoy.

	Rocky	Ajoy	Oreo	Conversion	Average Category Conversion	Rocky	Ajoy	Oreo
Most Often/Regular	8	0	18	P1M to Most often	20%	24%	0%	38%
P1M	34	6	48	P3M to P1M	68%	81%	67%	77%
P3M	42	9	62					
Ever Used (P1Y)	59	14	78	Ever used to P3M	64%	71%	64%	79%
Purchase Intent	36	15	49	Total aware to Ever used	59%	66%	28%	83%
Total Awareness	89	48	94					

Figure 6. Consumer Purchase Funnel 2021, Claygo Data

PREMIUM POSITIONING

Is the premium positioning that Ajoy intends to have already well perceived by the target consumer?

Ajoy’s price point is now the highest compared with other brands but less premium than Rocky and Oreo. By having current pricing but without having enough premium perception and value proposition understanding make difficult for Ajoy to stay relevant and promising as consumers just think that it is just an expensive product but not worth the price.

The data also shows that Ajoy’s higher price point currently cannot justify the premium-ness as the consumer still sees that the brand is not premium enough to have IDR 9000 price point. This is mainly because consumer does not really understand Ajoy’s value proposition. Current Ajoy’s price point is still not able to justify the premium positioning it wants to build yet. Thus the task is how to make Ajoy current price point acceptable and can reflect the premium positioning in the biscuit category.

Referring from internal company brand health data, it is found that Ajoy still has weak perception on premiumness and quality as the score of the two attributes are more than the norm of market average which shows there are more people who are thinking that Ajoy is not premium enough and has poor quality than other brands in the market. Ajoy needs to watch out for the ‘not premium/exclusive enough’ and ‘poor quality’ concerns that may harm its premium strategy and pose a potential threat to justify a higher price in consumers’ minds if not resolved.

Figure 7. Premium Perceptual Mapping, Analysed by Researcher

Table 1. Ajoy's Premium Perception Score, Claygo Data

Consumer Concerns	% of those aware, not consider for Ajoy	% of those aware, not consider for Market Average
Not premium or exclusive enough	14	12
Costs more than I am willing to pay	12	13
Poor quality	4	3

PREMIUM ATTRIBUTES

What are the premium brand attributes that Ajoy should improve to convey its premium positioning?

Through online questionnaire, researcher examines the premium perception by comparing Ajoy with competing brands based on three attributes which could characterize the premium perception:

- Worth the money** which shows that consumers believe that the brand’s price point is fair means to receive something that is reasonable for them and worth the money they paid or the effort they put in.
- High quality** which shows that the brand is adhering to a high standard of measurement, outstanding materials quality and the best features at the best value.
- Premium/ exclusive feeling which** shows that the brand is giving consistent premium or exclusive engagement that consumers wish with the brand. It includes the brand persona, tone & manner, and communication approach.

Table 1. Ajoy's Premium Attribute Score, Analysed by Researcher

	Norm (average)	AJOY	ROCKY	CHOCOLATOS	ASTOR	BENGBENG	OREO
Worth The Money	3,80	3,68	3,90	3,77	3,81	3,84	3,77
High Quality	3,77	3,49	4,09	3,43	3,67	3,72	3,82
Premium/ Exclusive Feeling	3,59	3,23	4,13	3,05	3,35	3,41	3,70

Based on the findings, to convey its intended premium positioning, Ajoy needs to improve the three important attributes to build premiumness namely worth the money, high quality, and premium/exclusive feeling as on all three attributes Ajoy still has a relatively lower score compared with the norms. On “worth the money” attribute, the highest score is achieved by Rocky the sister brand while Ajoy is on the lowest rank. The same situation happens on “high quality” attributes. On “premium/exclusive feeling” attribute Ajoy is slightly above Chocolatos but is still below the norm. These findings reflect that Ajoy needs to strengthen the brand message that highlights the required attribute to strengthen the premium positioning that it aims. Ajoy could reinforce its premium positioning by emphasizing more its promising ingredient sourcing which reflects the high quality product as it can help to justify

the premium-ness, highlighting the Japanese Claygo quality assured, and reinforcing the brand uniqueness through strong attribute and occasion association.

SWEET BISCUIT ATTRIBUTES

What are other important attributes in the sweet biscuit category that Ajoy should improve?

Through online questionnaire, researcher examines the perception towards the importance of snacking in sweet biscuit category by comparing Ajoy with competing brands based on seven attributes which could characterize the importance in sweet biscuit category:

- a. **indulgent** which shows that this brand is suitable as self-reward / guilty pleasure to relieve stress
- b. **convenient** which shows that this brand is packed conveniently, easy to carry and also practical to consume
- c. **lifestyle fit** which shows that this brand suits my lifestyle and needs, both for personal and social lifestyle
- d. **unique** which shows that this brand has a unique or different characteristic, or a different image that other biscuit brands don't have
- e. **trusted & popular** which shows that this brand is trusted and popular hence you have no doubt in it
- f. **happiness uplift** which shows that this brand can give you a happy feeling and wipe your gloom
- g. **mood booster** which shows that this brand can boost your mood, turn bad mood to good mood
- h. **good taste** which shows that this brand has a good taste which delight you

It has been found that the popularity and trustworthy attributes as well as convenient attributes influence the purchasing of 'Ajoy' in

the first place. Perhaps, the Claygo company reputation brings power to its brand and the product format gives convenience in snacking compared with others which may cause crumbs or mess. Then it is followed by attributes like good taste, unique, and indulgent. The uniqueness may come from the product format as well and the indulgence may come from the amount of chocolate inside the stick that can give enough pleasure.

Further analysis shows that attributes like convenience and unique are surpassing the index average which mean Ajoy has potential to strengthen these attributes. Meanwhile, on top three attributes which have the highest degree of importance namely good taste, mood booster, trusted & popular, Ajoy's scores are way behind the average. Thus, Ajoy needs to achieve more scores surpassing the average. Ajoy still has room to strengthen its perceptions compared to competitors, especially focusing on top emotional indulgent attributes.

Figure 8. Ajoy Sweet Biscuit Attribute VS Norm, Analysed by Researcher

Figure 9. Sweet Biscuit Attribute Among Brands, Analysed by Researcher

CONSUMPTION OCCASION

What are the occasion associations that are suitable for Ajoy?

Through online questionnaire, researcher examines what are the consumption occasion association in sweet biscuit category by comparing Ajoy with competing brands based on nine consumption occasions, the result is explained on figure 10:

1. A snack to accompany coffee/tea is dominated by Astor
2. A snack when you want to reward yourself/self-reward is dominated by Ajoy
3. A snack while on me time is dominated by Rocky
4. A snack while watching movies/tv shows is dominated by Rocky
5. After-meal snack instead of dessert is dominated by Bengbeng
6. A Snack while working/studying is dominated by Rocky
7. A Snack to accompany when on the go is dominated by Rocky
8. A snack for a picnic or enjoying a vacation somewhere is dominated by Rocky
9. A snack to accompany breaks/pauses between activities is dominated by Rocky

Figure 10. Occasion Association Among Brands, Analysed by Researcher

The result shows that 3 out of 9 occasions are dominated by Rocky, while Ajoy is mostly chosen as a snack that is suitable for self-reward as compared with total index average Ajoy is only able to surpass on “self-reward” occasion.

Compared with total index average Ajoy is only able to surpass on “self-reward” occasion with 29 points which means Ajoy can significantly own that occasion and bring it along with other sweet biscuit attributes and premium attributes. Furthermore, this self-reward occasion is closely associated with indulging in consumption linked with any product containing chocolate/cream/sweet confectionery. When people are stressed, they turn to comfort food and attempt to move toward products with sweets content. Despite the fact that emotional eating can make them better. The self-reward moment can be extended further to an unwinding and relaxing occasion after the hustle bustle to get through the day.

Figure 11. Ajoy Occasion Association VS Norm, Analysed by Researcher

BUSINESS SOLUTION

Identify Ajoy’s Low Brand Awareness Trigger

After identifying what are the low awareness triggers, it is found that media investment sufficiency might become the cause as it affected the low share of voice as well as low conversation about the brand in the social listening. hence, this study proposes several plan to overcome the barrier by implementing:

- a. Right targeting to potential consumers by having detailed persona which will help to understand further demographic, psychographic, and behavioral profiles especially on media consumption habits, so that Ajoy could have the right media touch point
- b. Knowing that Ajoy has low marketing investment budget concern, to maintain sufficient share of voice, the study proposes leveraging digital media only based on what the target audience consumes, so Ajoy’s brand awareness improvement effort could tap to the right audience with the right touch point and efficient media investment in the current low expenditure situation since the digital media platforms can give scalable advertisement output and possibly to custom the preferred audiences to optimize the limited budgets.

- c. Utilizing e-WOM to emphasize advocacy which leads to a potent source of awareness from friends, families, and relatives.

Table 3. Ajoy Purchase Conversion Barrier, Analysed by Researcher

Category	Non Consumers	Types of Barrier	Barrier Strength
Lack of strong reason to buy: Ajoy perceived to be less stand out, which makes people not attracted to try Ajoy in the first place	v	Product education barrier	soft
Lack of brand/product understanding : people don't understand what is Ajoy uniqueness and its offer compared with other brands	v	Product education barrier	soft
Value for money : For the same amount of money, they can get more other chocolate snacks due to promo that offered.	v	Price barrier	medium
Expensive: notably more pricey than Rocky, while Rocky is already perceived as expensive snack	v	Price barrier	medium
Not available in the purchase point near their house	v	Physical availability barrier	soft
Lack of communication: they cannot remember the brand when purchase products in sweet biscuit category	v	Mental availability barrier	soft

Identify Ajoy’s Low Purchase Conversion Trigger

The study has analyzed several triggers that cause Ajoy’s low purchase conversion (aware to ever purchase) trigger which include product education, mental availability, physical availability, and price barrier. to overcome the low purchase conversion triggers, this study proposes several initiatives namely :

- a. Mental availability barrier : leveraging brand awareness and ensuring the sufficiency and effectivity
- b. Product education barrier : emphasizing product knowledge by highlighting brand unique selling proposition and showing more product appeal which highlight “the sensation while consuming Ajoy” as Ajoy is premium snack with pleasant sensation from its melted soft chocolate in the mount and crunchy slender biscuit shell that can be consumed elegantly without getting messy, greasy, and sticky.
- c. Physical availability barrier : enlarging distribution coverage and working hand in hand with sales operation team
- d. Price barrier : Introducing Ajoy’s trial pack and utilizing regular promotion beside always emphasizing product knowledge to give premium price point judgment

Develop Ajoy’s Brand Message Corresponding to The Premium Positioning

The study has analyzed Ajoy’s brand message in the past 2020-2021 campaign, it is found that the brand message still could not reflect a strong perception of premium and high quality as consumer perception on both aspects is still neutral and not strong enough to give notable judgment. Hence, this study proposes a new formulation of the brand message which is able to emphasize the premium positioning that Ajoy aims to have by strengthening premium attributes, important sweet biscuit attributes, and consumption occasion. all the three elements are also expected to become Ajoy’s point of difference which will also raise consumer’s understanding and reason to believe toward the brand.

Thus, Ajoy has to strengthen the premium attributes as below:

- a. **Worth the money**
How to strengthen:

- Build an emotional connection with customers
- Encourage Indulgence by Convince consumers that they deserve to spend more to pamper themselves or loved ones
- Focus On Key Benefit That Commands The Higher Price

b. High quality (related with product element)

How to strengthen:

- emphasize the ingredient source that may come from certain region or specialty
- emphasize the certified ingredient that currently used for example by using RSPO standard vegetable oil or cocoa life which promotes 100% sustainably sourced cocoa
- emphasize on high technology that enable Claygo to produce a slender with 0.5 mm crispy biscuit stick with full amount of chocolate inside

c. Exclusive feeling

How to strengthen:

- have alpha female with elegant lifestyle as key opinion leader, face of the brand, or spokesperson of the brand
- be present in any high-end event or any event that relates with prime prospect interest, for example like Indonesian Fashion Week or Jazz Concert
- create a pop-up store that showcase Ajoy's premium and elegance in selected area like in high-end shopping mall, beach club, or exclusive airline lounge.
- develop a community event which consist of KOL and loyal users
- create a bundle SKU which consist of limited merchandise selection, else lunch a seasonal limited SKU

d. Flavor selection

How to strengthen:

- introduce a flavor range that is different from Rocky as current Ajoy flavor in Chocolate and Cookies Cream also owned by Rocky. the flavor selection may induce the premium specialty, for example like Belgian Chocolate, Japanese Matcha, New Zealand Vanilla Milk

Improve Important Attributes in the Sweet Biscuit Category

It has been found that the popularity and trustworthy attributes as well as convenient attributes influence the purchasing of 'Ajoy' in the first place. Perhaps, the Claygo company reputation brings power to its brand and the product format gives convenience in snacking compared with others which may cause crumbs or mess. Then it is followed by attributes like good taste, unique, and indulgent. The uniqueness may come from the product format as well and the indulgence may come from the amount of chocolate inside the stick that can give enough pleasure. Further analysis shows that attributes like convenience and unique are surpassing the index average which mean Ajoy has potential to strengthen these attributes. Meanwhile, on top three attributes which have the highest degree of importance namely good taste, mood booster, trusted & popular, Ajoy's scores are way behind the average. Thus, Ajoy needs to achieve more scores surpassing the average. Ajoy still has room to strengthen its perceptions compared to competitors, especially focusing on top emotional indulgent attributes.

Functional Benefit Related Attributes

a. Good taste

How to strengthen:

- Emphasize the chocolate inside and the crispy biscuit exterior, using selected high quality ingredients to create the ultimate indulgence in one stick with a melty and crunchy sensation in every bite, the velvety, smooth chocolate that is full from end to end, made from the world finest cocoa beans from West Africa, and the crispy biscuit exterior, in a slender and slim shape, made with whole wheat and baked in right temperature for extra crispiness.

b. Convenient

How to strengthen:

- emphasize the practicality of product format, with a firm crispy biscuit shell that covers the soft chocolate inside,

it makes Ajoy non messy, non-greasy, and non-sticky snack with the box packaging, it makes Ajoy practical to be carried anywhere, anytime.

Emotional Benefit Related Attributes

a. Indulgent

Visualize the relaxed and indulged effect when consumers feel a melt sensation from the abundant chocolate cream and wrapped in crispy biscuit

b. Mood Booster

Expose combination of dark chocolate bitter taste, milky taste, savory taste of wheat are considered to be able to increase the mood

c. Rewarding

Expose Ajoy individual consumption. The vibe of Ajoy is premium, elegant, and classy. Majority consumers prefer to consume alone rather than sharing due to the portion and the amount of chocolate is suitable to release stress while me-time and as self-reward.

Formulate The Brand Campaign and Message

Furthermore, researcher propose a campaign idea which would resemble all things that Ajoy would like to convey to its prime prospect in order to increase meaningful brand awareness and purchase conversion by building the right perception of Ajoy's premium positioning. Thus, the campaign ideation is clarified as below:

Campaign idea: Showing feel good, taste good of Ajoy consumer experience, With Ajoy pleasure can be enjoyed anytime, slipped in between their busy schedule, ups and down within their daily routine, facing their roller coaster life without guilt.

Message Pillar:

1. Taste good

A perfect combination of crunchy exterior and velvety chocolate filling in slick stick format without any mess nor crumbs, which makes Ajoy a snack that can ensure indulgence in every bite.

2. Feel good

ensuring that pleasure endures forever, allowing everyone to experience pleasure at their own pace, whenever they choose, whenever they are able, whenever they are required. Ajoy can be induced during any activity and is marketed as a "relaxation alarm."

Tagline: The Ajoyable Moment.

Conveyed emotion: As Always I strive for excellence in both career and life throughout the day, there is never an uninteresting moment in my life. Every day, I set aside time to relax and reward myself for a sense of accomplishment.

Distinctive tone & manner: Relax, elegant, premium, mature.

Campaign Deliverables: New flavour line, new advertising materials including video and key visual, brand spokesperson and key opinion leaders.

Identify The Consumption Occasion Associations

The result shows that 3 out of 9 occasions are dominated by Rocky, while Ajoy is mostly chosen as a snack that is suitable for self-reward as compared with total index average Ajoy is only able to surpass on "self-reward" occasion. Furthermore, this self-reward occasion is closely associated with indulging in consumption linked with any product containing chocolate/cream/sweet confectionery. When people are stressed, they turn to comfort food and attempt to move toward products with sweets content. Despite the fact that emotional eating can make them better. The self-reward moment can be extended further to an unwinding and relaxing occasion after the hustle bustle to get through the day. Thus, it is recommended to tap into below occasion:

a. Priority 1 : Self reward - unwinding moment

Consumers can use Ajoy to unwind due to the relaxing and indulging effect from the combination of textures between the chocolate filling and crunchy biscuits, an intense chocolate taste, and a melting sensation that makes Ajoy provide a relaxing and indulging effect which is effective as a unwind or self-reward snack.

b. Priority 2 : Beverage companion

Ajoy for any kind of beverage taste. The right sweet taste (not too sweet) with a crunchy biscuit texture is considered a suitable

snack to accompany consumers to enjoy their drinks (can be an ideal snack for sweetened or unsweetened drinks).

c. Snack while working or studying

A light bite to recharge spirit and energy in between activity or job. Staying motivated and productive with the perfect combination and composition of taste from chocolate and biscuits is suitable to lift their spirits between activities or jobs undertaken. No effort is needed, no mess to worry, a perfect portion which is not too fulfilling.

Formulate Integrated Marketing Communication Initiative

The media touch points will take the role as tools to convey any messages that Ajoy wants to deliver to the prime prospects. As explained in the previous chapter that Ajoy currently has a small marketing budget, this study will propose a digital based media mix to follow current investment that Claygo has for Ajoy to build the brand in the Indonesia market. researcher will utilize the moment of truth journey which consist of consevative stages namely the stimulus, the zero moment of truth, the first moment of truth, the second moment of truth and finally the ultimate moment of truth which become the step to bring advocacy to life.

Table 4. Proposed IMC for Ajoy, Analysed by Researcher

	Stimulus	Zero Moment of Truth	First Moment of Truth	Second Moment of Truth	Ultimate Moment of Truth
Objective	Drive rapid brand awareness and salience of Ajoy	Presenting Ajoy’s USP and build owned consumption occasion	Encouraging delightful shopping experience which make Ajoy appeal to catch attention in store & ecommerce	Emphasize truly experiences with Ajoy. occur before purchase (trial) and after purchase (consume)	Driving the last mile conversion to encourage advocacy and repeat purchase
Creative Deliverables / Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ads Video with 6s, 15s, and 30s - Static key visuals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KOL product review content activation - branded effect Tiktok 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sampling activation - product catalogue display 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ajoy loyalty program - Ajoy UGC activation (photo contest) 	
Media Touch Points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●OLV DV 360 - TrueView and Bumper ●Google Programmatic Display ●Meta Reach & Frequency ●Tiktok Display Ads Reach & Frequency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●KOL utilization & amplification ●Tiktok Branded Effect ●Meta retargeting ●OLV ad sequencing ●Search engine optimization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●Always On Tokopedia Display Network (TDN) ●Tiktok shop ●Meta CPAS ●Affiliate Marketing - Tokopedia ●Grivy - ads with redeemable coupon ●Home Tester Club - sampling utilization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●referral program by using shareable unique code ●point redemption program 	
Target Audience	Mass audience within targeted group Location : Indonesia Age & Gender: 25-	Retargeting audience who engages on stimulus ads, KOL	Retargeting audience who engaged on stimulus ads and shoppers on certain account, might also be possible to utilize account like Alfamart and	Retargeting audiences who have purchased Ajoy minimum	

	44, Female Interests: Coffee shop, Food, Lifestyle, Chocolate, Biscuits, Desserts, Cake, Bakeries or Iced coffee, Beauty & Personal Care, Lifestyle, Coffee shop, Luxury goods, Online Shopping, Food & Beverage, Snacks Behaviors: Engaged shoppers or People in Indonesia who prefer mid-value and high-value goods	native followers who share similar interest with the KOL	Indomaret database		past 3 months purchase
Desired Consumer Response	I know Ajoy	I am getting interested with Ajoy	I want to look for Ajoy	I buy and try Ajoy	I recommend Ajoy to others
Overall KPI	Total Brand Awareness	Purchase Intention and Product favourability	Ever Purchase & Past 1 year purchase		Advocacy ad Repeat Rate

CONCLUSION

1. Brand awareness is surely a basic issue to be solved as it becomes the first entrance gate in the consumer journey. Knowing that Ajoy has limited resources, it is recommended to utilize digital platforms both for ensuring sufficient share of voice as well as effective and measurable investment. Thus, Ajoy could optimize the brand awareness level with the right target and right touch points.
2. On top of that, ensuring meaningful awareness is also important to survive in the competition. Thus, increasing purchase conversion to convert people who are already aware of purchasing is necessary for Ajoy to increase its business size in terms of penetration rate and market share. Overcoming the barrier to purchase is the key. This study has revealed four major barriers namely product knowledge, price, mental and physical availability. The study also recommends solutions to tackle the barriers as well.
3. In correlation with the product knowledge barrier, Ajoy has to take a look at its premium positioning as well. The data shows Ajoy’s higher price point currently cannot justify the premium-ness as the consumer still sees that the brand is not premium enough to have IDR 9000 price point By having current pricing but without having enough premium perception and value proposition understanding make difficult for Ajoy to stay relevant and promising as consumers just think that it is just an expensive product but not worth the price. The product knowledge barrier caused low reason to purchase as well as consumer does not understand what is Ajoy unique selling proposition among competitors
4. Hence, Ajoy needs to tackle any barriers that caused the low brand awareness and low purchase conversion. On top of that, it is also needed to revamp the brand message formulation which is able to emphasize more Ajoy's USP and strengthen

premium positioning that Ajoy aims to have. And finally, integrated marketing communication initiative and campaign idea is formulated in accordance with the designed brand message

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